

Folding Simulation of Square Twist Origami using Planar Tensegrity Model

Lidong ZHU^a, Jingyao ZHANG*

* Dept. of Architecture & Architectural Engineering, Kyoto University
C2 Building, Kyotodaigaku-katsura, Nishikyo-ku, Kyoto, 615-8540, Japan
zhang@archi.kyoto-u.ac.jp

Abstract

Rigid paper panels are commonly modeled using truss or panel-hinge structures in origami folding simulations. The traditional truss model with more than three edges, such as quadrilaterals with members along the four edges and two diagonals, is unstable due to out-of-plane mechanisms. This paper proposes modeling quadrilateral papers as planar (X-form) tensegrity structures to address instability issues. Prestress in planar tensegrities ensures stability and planarity by eliminating redundant infinitesimal mechanisms. The strain energy of tensegrity can easily check the rigidity after the equilibrium condition is strictly satisfied. This paper proposed two methods, incremental enforced displacement and repeated form-finding, that simulated non-rigid and rigid folding of the square twist origami. For the rigid folding, the strain energy remains unchanged. For the non-rigid one, the strain energy reveals bistable equilibrium states of the tensegrity, corresponding to the flat-unfolded and flat-folded states of origami at the start and end of folding.

Keywords: Planar tensegrity, Square twist origami, Folding simulation, Rigid fold, Form-finding

1. Introduction

Along with the developments in origami designs and applications, many modeling methods have been utilized to simulate origami folding. Kinematic methods such as Spherical Trigonometry [1] and Loop Closure Conditions [2] simulate thin, rigid origami without panel thickness and deformation. They cannot capture deformations such as bending and twisting of paper panels. In comparison, mechanical methods, such as truss or panel-hinge models, can simulate rigid and non-rigid origami. For the truss or truss-based models, the folding path can be calculated by analyzing the mechanism modes if the origami is rigid-foldable. However, for paper panels with more than three edges, such as quadrilaterals, the traditional truss model—with members along the four edges and two diagonals—is unstable. This instability occurs because infinitesimal rotations (mechanisms) around the diagonals exist within the triangular elements, leading to a loss of planarity. To address this issue, Schenk et al. [3] triangulated the quadrilateral facet into two triangles and placed a spring between them to eliminate out-of-plane mechanisms. Zhang et al. [4] complemented a dummy point outside the quadrilateral plane to create a pyramid-like three-dimensional truss model. Hayakawa et al. [5] exclude redundant infinitesimal mechanisms based on the existence condition of the second-order infinitesimal mechanism. These methods significantly increase the degrees of freedom or require complicated analysis, resulting in high computational costs for the folding simulation.

This study proposes modeling paper panels with more than three edges as planar tensegrity structures, which refer to those whose components (nodes, struts, cables) lie in a single plane. Specifically, quadrilateral panels are represented as X-form tensegrities (kite frames) consisting of two intersecting compressive struts along the diagonals and four tensile cables along the edges, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (a). As illustrated in Fig. 1 (b), the existence of prestress stabilizes the structure and maintains planarity by eliminating redundant infinitesimal mechanisms. This model can also be applied to non-rigid origami

with moderate twist deformation where geometrical stiffness [6] due to prestress generates a storing force for planarity.

This study simulates the square twist's non-rigid and rigid folding through incremental enforced displacement and repeated form-finding. The square twist has four types due to four kinds of mountain-valley (MV) crease assignments, among which two are non-rigid-foldable, such as S-T-1 (square twist type-1) in Fig. 2 (a). Two are rigid-foldable, such as S-T-2 in Fig. 2 (b), where red dashed lines indicate valley creases and blue dashed lines indicate mountain creases. Hull et al. [7] found that S-T-1 can be modified to M-S-T-1 to become rigid-foldable by augmenting a temporary diagonal crease to the central square, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (c), where the grey dashed line indicates a temporary crease. The rigidity of folding (modified) square twists has been proven in research by Feng et al. [8]. In this paper, it is checked by the variation of strain energy after the equilibrium condition is strictly satisfied.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the innovative planar tensegrity model and investigates the out-of-plane stiffness of the X-form tensegrity. Section 3 presents the two folding simulation methods using incremental enforced displacement and repeated form-finding. Section 4 presents the numerical examples of folding (modified) square twist origami. The conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

Figure 1. Unit tensegrity model

Figure 2. MV assignment of (modified) square twist

2. Planar tensegrity modeling

The classical square twist has nine quadrilaterals, 12 creases, 12 edges, and 16 vertices containing four inner vertices. We model quadrilateral papers in the square twist as X-form tensegrities, consisting of two intersecting compressive struts along the diagonals and four tensile cables along the edges. Therefore, the tensegrity model has 16 nodes and 42 members containing 24 cables and 18 struts.

2.1. Prestress of unit tensegrity

Denoting a as a positive scalar to indicate the prestress level, the prestress \mathbf{s}_f of the unit tensegrity satisfies

$$\mathbf{D}(a\mathbf{v}_f) = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}_f = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times 6}$ is the equilibrium matrix. $\mathbf{v}_f \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the null space vector of \mathbf{D} whose direction is adjusted to make diagonal members compressive, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (b).

2.2. Investigation of out-of-plane stiffness

We assume all members have a unit cross-sectional area $A = 1$, struts have the same elastic modulus E_s , and cables have the same elastic modulus E_c . Then the tangent stiffness $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times 12}$ of the tensegrity model can be derived by summing the elastic stiffness \mathbf{K}_e and the geometric stiffness \mathbf{K}_g [6], i.e.:

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_e + \mathbf{K}_g \quad (2)$$

The geometric stiffness due to prestress will provide a considerable out-of-plane stiffness even

Figure 3. Out-of-plane stiffness

(a) Assembled prestress (b) Assembled model

Figure 4. Tensegrity modeling of square twist

when the tensegrity is in the planar state. We gradually lift one corner outside the tensegrity plane to investigate this stiffness further. The reactive force-displacement relation is illustrated in Fig. 3. We found stiffness along the lifting direction is initially zero and then exponentially increases when no prestress is introduced, see those lines without markers. Nevertheless, non-zero stiffness can be confirmed even in the planar state after the introduction of prestress, see those red lines with markers.

Analyzing the null space of \mathbf{K}_e and \mathbf{K} of planar X-form tensegrity, we found the X-form structure without prestress has seven mechanism modes, including six rigid body motions and one out-of-plane infinitesimal mechanism. However, this redundant mechanism is eliminated by introducing prestress.

2.3. Assembly

We assemble the entire model and determine whether each member is a cable, or a strut based on the sign of assembled prestress by summing prestress of shared creases as illustrated in Fig. 4. Where red members are struts with negative prestress, and blue members are cables with positive prestress. Analyzing the tangent stiffness of the assembled model, we identified four mechanism modes, excluding the rigid body motions. Compared to the 13 mechanism modes in the truss model without prestress, nine infinitesimal mechanisms are eliminated, highlighting the impact of prestress on the structural behavior.

3. Folding simulation using two methods

3.1. Non-rigid folding simulation using enforced displacement

3.1.1. Incremental enforced displacement

Suppose there are n^c enforced displacements and n^f fixed degrees of freedom to eliminate rigid body motions. The tensegrity model has in total $3 \times 16 - n^f - n^c$ degrees of freedom. The equilibrium equation considering enforced displacement can be described as follows

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{11} & \mathbf{K}_{12} \\ \mathbf{K}_{21} & \mathbf{K}_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{d}} \\ \mathbf{d} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{R} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{K}_{ij} are the partial tangent stiffness and $\mathbf{R} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n^f+n^c}$ are the reactive forces of fixed nodes and constrained nodes. $\mathbf{0} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48-n^f-n^c}$ means no loads are applied to the structure. And $\bar{\mathbf{d}} = (\boldsymbol{\delta}^T \mathbf{0}^T)^T$ are the constrained displacements containing incremental enforced displacements $\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n^c}$ and the displacements of fixed nodes $\mathbf{0} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n^f}$. The displacements $\mathbf{d} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48-n^f-n^c}$ of free nodes can be derived as follows

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{K}_{22}^+ (\mathbf{0} - \mathbf{K}_{21} \bar{\mathbf{d}}) \quad (4)$$

Here, in case of singularity of $\mathbf{K}_{22} \in \mathfrak{R}^{(48-n^f-n^c) \times (48-n^f-n^c)}$, pseudo-inverse \mathbf{K}_{22}^+ [9] is used instead of inverse \mathbf{K}_{22}^{-1} . Then the nodal coordinates $\mathbf{X} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48}$ are updated as follows

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X} + (\bar{\mathbf{d}}^T \mathbf{d}^T)^T \quad (5)$$

This calculation for enforced displacement is repeated, followed by the process of equilibrium-finding.

3.1.2. Equilibrium-finding

The nodal coordinate derived in Eq. (5) is a prediction that may not satisfy the equilibrium condition in large deformation problems. The unbalanced forces are calculated by using the partial force density matrices \mathbf{E}_{ij} [6] as follows

$$\mathbf{f} = (\mathbf{I} \otimes (\mathbf{E}_{21} \quad \mathbf{E}_{22}))\mathbf{X} \quad (6)$$

Then, the nodal displacement for equilibrium correction can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{d} = -\mathbf{K}_{22}^+ \mathbf{f} \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{d}} = \mathbf{0}$ is used. Finally, the nodal coordinates are recalculated as

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X} + (\mathbf{0}^T \mathbf{d}^T)^T \quad (8)$$

Equations (6-8) are repeated until the unbalanced forces vanish.

3.2. Rigid folding simulation using form-finding

3.2.1. Rigid folding

Rigid folding of origami refers to the process where papers are not bent or deformed; only rotation around the crease is allowed, which means the member lengths or the strain energy remain unchanged in a truss-based structure. If we investigate the potential energy of the structure, we find its variation $\Delta\Pi$ the same as the variation of strain energy ΔU because origami or tensegrity is self-equilibrium, and no external work is applied, i.e., $\Delta\Pi = \Delta U - \Delta W = \Delta U$. Then the Taylor expansion of variation of potential energy or strain energy is as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta U &= \sum \frac{\partial U}{\partial X_j} \Delta X_j + \frac{1}{2} \sum \sum \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X_i \partial X_j} \Delta X_i \Delta X_j + \frac{1}{6} \sum \sum \sum \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial X_i \partial X_j \partial X_k} \Delta X_i \Delta X_j \Delta X_k \dots \\ &= \Delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{s} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{K} \Delta \mathbf{X} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{s} \in \mathfrak{R}^{42}$ are member axial forces, $\Delta \mathbf{X} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48}$ are nodal displacements of all nodes. The term $\Delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{s}$ is corresponding to the self-equilibrium condition, which is satisfied automatically, and the other terms are corresponding to the rigid folding condition. We say any small nodal displacements $\Delta \mathbf{X}$ are rigid folding only if they make $\frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{K} \Delta \mathbf{X} + \dots$ equal to zero.

3.2.2. Linear prediction

From Eq. (9), we know the rigid folding condition has infinite expansion terms, so solving all the terms to derive the rigid folding is impossible. Yet, we can solve its first term to derive the linear prediction of rigid folding, i.e.:

$$\frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{K} \Delta \mathbf{X} = 0 \quad (10)$$

The result of this equation lies in the null space of the tangent stiffness matrix. In the case of multiple mechanism modes, Eq. (10) merely can't yield a specific solution. We consider geometric constraints about the rotation angles of creases to determine one solution.

We divide angles of creases $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ as controlled angle and uncontrolled angles, and denote them as $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2$, respectively. The relation between the variation of rotation angles and nodal displacements under small displacement scale is as follows [3]

$$\begin{pmatrix} J_{11} & J_{12} \\ J_{21} & J_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{d} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\theta_1 \\ \Delta\theta_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Where $\mathbf{0} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n^f}$ represent displacements of fixed nodes and $\mathbf{d} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48-n^f}$ represent displacements of free nodes. $\Delta\theta_1$ and $\Delta\theta_2$ are the target variations of controlled and uncontrolled rotation angles, where positive angles represent valley creases and negative ones represent mountain creases. We satisfy the first row of Eq. (11) corresponding to controlled angles, and satisfy the second row corresponding to uncontrolled angles as much as possible. Therefore, the purpose of linear prediction is to solve the following problem

$$\min_{\mathbf{d} \in \mathfrak{R}^{48-n^f}} \|J_{22}\mathbf{d} - \Delta\theta_2\| \quad (12.1)$$

$$\text{s. t. } \mathbf{K}_{22}\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0} \quad (12.2)$$

$$J_{12}\mathbf{d} = \Delta\theta_1 \quad (12.3)$$

We use pseudo inverse operation and null space projection matrix to solve Problem (12). The main idea is finding a particular solution \mathbf{d}^* that satisfies constraints

$$\mathbf{d}^* = \mathbf{P}_k (J_{12}\mathbf{P}_k)^+ \Delta\theta_1 \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{P}_k is the null space projection matrix of \mathbf{K}_{22} . And then adjust the solution to minimize the objective function within the null space of constraints

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}^* + \mathbf{P}_{kj} (J_{22}\mathbf{P}_{kj})^+ (\Delta\theta_2 - J_{22}\mathbf{d}^*) \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{P}_{kj} is the null space projection matrix of $\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{22} \\ J_{12} \end{pmatrix}$. Finally nodal coordinates can be recalculated using Eq. (8). The solution of linear prediction doesn't exactly satisfy the rigid folding condition because only one term (second order term of Taylor expansion) is considered.

3.2.3. Folding path correction via form-finding

Form-finding is used to correct the rigid folding path. Form-finding is a technique widely used to find the equilibrium figuration of spatial structures. In this paper, we use the form-finding method that is not significantly different from the equilibrium-finding approach in the enforced displacement method, i.e., repeating Equations (6-8) until the unbalanced forces vanish. Merely, in form-finding method, there are only six fixed degrees of freedom eliminating the six rigid body motions, no enforced displacement, i.e.: $\Delta\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{0}^T \in \mathfrak{R}^6 \ \mathbf{d}^T \in \mathfrak{R}^{48-6})^T$.

Figure 5. Interpretation of rigid folding simulation using form-finding.

We use a one-bar system to interpret the form-finding method, where one end of the bar is fixed, and the other is free, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The rigid folding path of the free node is a circle around the

fixed point. Fig. 5 shows the strain energy function of the nodal coordinates, where the red line is a rigid folding path lying on the plane of $U = U_0$, \mathbf{X}' are the coordinates after linear prediction and \mathbf{X} are the rigid folding coordinates lying on the rigid folding path. As illustrated, the essence of form-finding is to search for the nearest neutral-equilibrium position (flat region) to the linear prediction position. Notably, if the origami is not rigid-foldable, the form-finding will converge to the initial position \mathbf{X}_0 , and it may also converge to the position where the strain energy is different from the initial strain energy in case of multi-stable equilibrium (local minimum). Therefore, to ensure the result is a correct rigid folding, we have to check whether $\mathbf{X} \neq \mathbf{X}_0$ and $U(\mathbf{X}) = U_0$ are satisfied. The strain energy can be obtained as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{k}_0(\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{L}_0)^2 \mathbf{L}_0^{-1}\|_1 \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_0 \in \mathfrak{R}^{42 \times 42}$ is the diagonal matrix of member axial stiffness, $\mathbf{L} \in \mathfrak{R}^{42 \times 42}$ are the member lengths according to the current nodal coordinates, and $\mathbf{L}_0 \in \mathfrak{R}^{42 \times 42}$ are the initial member lengths without prestress. \mathbf{L}_0 can be obtained using

$$\mathbf{L}_0^{-1} = \mathbf{L}_p^{-1}(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{k}_0^{-1} \mathbf{S}_p) \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{L}_p \in \mathfrak{R}^{m \times m}$ are member lengths after prestressing and are also the lengths of edges and diagonals of the crease pattern, and $\mathbf{S}_p \in \mathfrak{R}^{42 \times 42}$ are assembled prestresses.

4. Numerical examples

In the following examples, axial stiffnesses of cables and struts are $E_c A = 1 \times 10^4$ and $E_s A = 1 \times 10^9$ respectively, the prestress level a is 1×10^4 , and the side length of the entire paper is 4.

4.1. Non-rigid folding of Type-1 using enforced displacement

Figure 6. Non-rigid folding simulation of S-T-1

In the non-rigid folding simulation, we use the enforced displacement method. The S-T-1's MV assignment, shown in Fig. 2 (a), is 90-degree rotationally symmetric. Therefore, we can assign the direction of enforced displacement that points from four corners to the center of the central square. The step size is $\delta = \sqrt{2}/100$. Six constraints are applied to the central square to eliminate the six rigid body motions. Yet, it should be noted that the structure's initial state is perfectly planar; in-plane enforced displacements will cause in-plane deformation instead of folding. Thus, we previously imposed a small

out-of-plane displacement on four corners to address this issue. The folding simulation is shown in Fig. 6, where black arrows indicate the directions of enforced displacements, and Bezier spline and surface are used to generate approximate visualized paper models. Out-of-plane deformation in unit tensegrities can be captured, and correspondingly, twists of papers can be observed in the visualized paper models.

Figure 7. Variation of energy and forces.

Figure 8. Bi-stable equilibrium of practical S-T-1

The variations of strain energy and reactive forces of four enforced nodes during folding are illustrated in Fig. 7. We find that the energy variation has two local minimums at the start and end of the folding, where the reactive forces along four enforced displacements are zero and increasing. Therefore, they are in a stable equilibrium along the enforced direction. On the contrary, the energy variation reaches a local peak during folding at the 110th iteration, where the reactive forces are zero and decreasing. Therefore, it is in an unstable equilibrium along the enforced direction. These points can be interpreted regarding the practical folding of square twist origami, as illustrated in Fig. 8. The two stable equilibrium points represent origami's unfolded and folded states, which are perfectly planar if neglecting the paper's thickness. The unstable equilibrium point represents a critical transition point for the origami. If the folding origami is released before this point, it returns to the unfolded state. If the folding origami is released after the equilibrium point, it automatically transitions to the folded state.

4.2. Rigid folding of Type-2 and Type-4 using form-finding

We use the form-finding method for rigid folding simulation, where six constraints are applied to the central square to eliminate rigid body motions. Repeated linear prediction that solves Problem (12) will rotate creases by the target incremental rotation angles. Form-finding is performed after every linear prediction process to balance the structure to satisfy the rigid folding condition. The square twist origami has one mechanism mode in the folding state; therefore, we must control at least one crease during folding. However, in an unfolded state, the origami has four mechanism modes, where the origami may bifurcate into two rigid foldings: S-T-2 and square twist type-4 (S-T-4). In this paper, we use the MV assignment to guide the right type of rigid folding. For example, in S-T-2, the MV assignment and its controlled creases are shown in Fig. 9 (a), where the solid line is the controlled crease. The target incremental rotation angles of creases are assigned as follows

$$\Delta\theta = \theta(MV_{st2})/m \quad (17)$$

where $\theta(MV_{st2})$ are rotation angles obtained from the MV assignment of S-T-2. If the crease is mountain, then $\theta = -\pi$, if the crease is valley, then $\theta = \pi$. And m is an integer that controls the folding speed, typically, $m = 50$ in this example. The simulation result and the variation of strain energy is illustrated in Fig. 10 (a) and Fig. 11 (a), respectively. In the example of S-T-4, we use the MV assignment MV_{st4} , as illustrated in Fig. 9 (b), to derive target incremental rotation angles based on Eq. (17). The simulation result and variation of strain energy are illustrated in Fig. 10 (b) and Fig. 11 (b), respectively. Based on the changing rotation angles and unchanged strain energy, we can conclude the results are rigid folding. The iterations were more than 50 because we have done 2 more iterations to eliminate the accumulated errors of rotation angles. But we do not expand on this in this paper.

(a) S-T-2 (b) S-T-4
 Figure 9. MV assignment of square twist

(a) S-T-2 (b) S-T-4
 Figure 10. Rigid folding path of square twist

(a) S-T-2 (b) S-T-4
 Figure 11. Variation of strain energy of square twist

4.3. Rigid folding of modified Type-1 using form-finding

In the example of M-S-T-1, the tensegrity model differs from the classical square twist. The assembled prestress is zero in the diagonal member of the central square; see black line in Fig. 12 (a). We treat this member as a struct member. The assembled model is illustrated in Fig. 12 (b). This model has 16 nodes and 41 members, containing 24 cables and 17 struts.

(a) Assembled prestress

(b) Assembled model

Figure 12. Tensegrity modeling of M-S-T-1

(a) Step 1

(b) Step 2

Figure 13. MV assignment of M-S-T-1

The origami has an additional temporary crease along the diagonal of the central square, which will turn flat at the end of folding. Then, the final folded state is identical to the S-T-1. The folding of M-S-T-1 consists of two steps. The M-S-T has two mechanism modes during the folding process; therefore, we must control at least two creases. The MV assignments and controlled creases of two steps are illustrated in Fig. 13. Each step is a flat-folding; therefore, we can also use Eq. (17) to assign target rotation angles for the first step by using the MV assignment of M-S-T-1 in the first step (MV_{mst1}^1). However, the second step's start rotation angles are no longer zeros. We use the angle differences between two MV assignments of two steps instead, i.e.:

$$\text{Step 1: } \Delta\theta^1 = \theta(MV_{mst1}^1)/m \quad (18.1)$$

$$\text{Step 2: } \Delta\theta^2 = (\theta(MV_{mst1}^2) - \theta(MV_{mst1}^1))/m \quad (18.2)$$

where $m = 50$ in this example. If we accumulate rotation angles by calculating $(\Delta\theta^1 + \Delta\theta^2) \times m$, we get $\theta(MV_{mst1}^2)$, which is identical to the rotation angles of MV assignment of S-T-1 ($\theta(MV_{st1})$). The simulation result and the variation of strain energy are illustrated in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, respectively, where Step 1 is Iter. 1~69, and Step 2 is Iter. 70~116.

Figure 14. Rigid folding path of M-S-T-1

Figure 15. Strain energy variation of M-S-T-1

We can conclude that the result is rigid folding based on the changing rotation angles and unchanged strain energy. The origami is flat at the end of folding, and its MV crease assignment is the same as that of S-T-1 if we check its rotation angles. As illustrated in Fig. 14, the angles of controlled angles did not change linearly as expected, especially in Step 1, which means the rotation angles did not precisely satisfy the predetermined target angles.

5. Conclusions

The proposed planar tensegrity model can eliminate redundant infinitesimal mechanisms for quadrilateral papers. The geometric stiffness due to prestress will provide a considerable out-of-plane stiffness for the tensegrity model even in the planar state. The proposed two folding simulation methods successfully simulate the folding of rigid and non-rigid square twist origami. For non-rigid square twist origami, the strain energy variation reveals two stable equilibrium states, corresponding to the unfolded and flat-folded states of origami, and one unstable equilibrium state, corresponding to the critical transition point. For rigid fold, the linear prediction using target rotation angles obtained from the MV assignment can guide different rigid-foldable types of square twists. The changing configurations and unchanged strain energies of origamis reveal that the square twist Type-2 and Type-4 are rigid-foldable. The modified square twist Type-1 example demonstrates that the form-finding method is also effective for simulating folding origami with multiple mechanism modes. Yet, in this case, the effectiveness of controlling multiple angles in this method needs improvement.

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